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Research Article

**FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF TRANSDERMAL
PATCHES BY USING PREGABALIN****Dr.K.L.Senthilkumar *¹, P.D. Gokulan *², M.Darshini*³, R.Dhivyabharathi*³,
B.Sreedhar*³, S. Hariprasath*³***¹ Principal, Sri Vijay Vidyalaya College of Pharmacy, Dharmapuri, Tamilnadu.*² Professor, Sri Vijay Vidyalaya College of Pharmacy, Dharmapuri, Tamilnadu.*³ B.Pharm Students, Sri Vijay Vidyalaya College of Pharmacy, Dharmapuri, Tamilnadu.**Abstract:**

The present study aimed to develop and evaluate transdermal patches of Pregabalin using Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose (HPMC) and ethyl cellulose (EC) as polymers and Polyethylene glycol (PEG) as permeation enhancer, Propylene glycol (PG) as plasticizer. Pregabalin is an anticonvulsant and analgesic agent commonly used to treat epilepsy, neuropathic pain and fibromyalgia. Transdermal patches were prepared by Solvent evaporation method and evaluated for physicochemical properties like film thickness, weight variation, folding endurance, moisture content and drug content. The result suggest that the developed transdermal patches of Pregabalin could provide a promising alternative to oral administration, offering improved bioavailability, reduced sideeffect ,enhanced patient compliance.

Key words: Transdermal patches, Pregabalin, Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose, Propylene glycol

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INTRODUCTION:

Pregabalin is a medication primarily used to treat neuropathic pain, generalized anxiety disorder, fibromyalgia, and as an adjunctive therapy for seizures. It is an anticonvulsant drug that acts by modulating the release of excitatory neurotransmitters in the central nervous system, providing relief from pain and reducing seizure activity. The structure consists of a hexanoic acid (a six-carbon chain with a carboxyl group) backbone, with an amino group ($-NH_2$) and a methyl group ($-CH_3$) attached to specific carbon atoms along the chain. Half life is Approximately 6 hours. This relatively short half-life allows for twice-daily dosing in most cases. Dose in neuropathic Pain: 75 mg twice daily. This can be increased to 150 mg twice daily based on patient response. Fibromyalgia: 75 mg twice daily, may be increased to 150 mg twice daily after 1 week. Seizures: Initial dose of 150mg per day, divided into two doses. It may be increased to 600 mg per day based on clinical response.

Figure 1: Structure of Pregabalin

Pregabalin is an anticonvulsant and analgesic medication. It is structurally related to gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) but does not act on GABA receptors. Pregabalin is primarily used to treat neuropathic pain, seizures, and generalized anxiety disorder (GAD). It is also approved for the management of fibromyalgia. Pregabalin helps reduce nerve activity by interacting with

calcium channels in the brain and spinal cord, reducing the release of excitatory neurotransmitters involved in pain and seizure processes.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

The polymers HPMC K15M from colorcon asia pvt, goa. Polyvinyl pyrrolidone, poly ethylene glycol brought from bangalore fine chemicals. Ethyl cellulose, Propylene glycol were brought from isochem laboratories.

Preparation of standard graph of Pregabalin

A spectrophotometric method based on the measurement of absorbance at 206 nm in phosphate buffer of pH 7.2 was used in the present study for the estimation of Pregabalin in the formulations. The standard solution of Pregabalin was subsequently diluted with phosphate buffer of pH 7.2 to obtain a series of dilutions containing 2,4,6,8 and 10 μ g of Pregabalin in 1ml solution. The absorbance of these solutions was measured in UV-Visible spectrophotometer at 206 nm using phosphate buffer of pH 7.2 as blank.

Preparation of films

Matrix films are casted on glass mould (petri plate) by solvent casting method. Three types transdermal films were prepared as the formula. All the preformulation contains propylene glycol as plasticizer. Polymers HPMC K15M and ethyl cellulose were dissolved in 4ml of methanol until it forms a homogeneous solution. Then the drug (Pregabalin) was added slowly in the polymeric solution and stirred on the magnetic stirrer to obtain the uniform solution. To this solution required amount of drug was added, and subsequently PG and PVP were added keeping the drug concentration constant in each formulation and stirred continuously to form a homogeneous mixture. The solution was poured into the Petri dish and dried at room temperature for 24 hrs. An inverted funnel was placed over the mould to prevent fast evaporation of the methanol. Patches were prepared by cutting and packed in aluminum foil and stored in a desiccators until further use.

Table 1: Formulation of transdermal films

Formulation Code	Pregabalin (mg)	Ethyl cellulose(mg)	HPMC K15M(mg)	PVP (mg)	PEG (ml)	PG (ml)	Methanol (ml)
F1	15	70	80	100	50	2	4
F2	15	50	60	75	50	2	4
F3	15	100	100	50	50	2	4

EVALUATION OF TRANSDERMAL FILMS

Physicochemical evaluation

1. Physical Appearance

All the prepared transdermal patches were visually inspected for clarity,color, flexibility and smoothness, uniformity, entrapment of air bubbles or precipitation of drug.

2. Film Thickness

The thickness of prepared patch was measured at three different places using a screw gauge and mean values were calculated .

3. Weight Variation

Weight variation was studied by individually weighing 3 randomly selected films. Such determination was performed for each formulation. The individual weight should not deviate from the average weight.

4. Folding Endurance

A strip of specific area of film was taken evenly and repeatedly folded at the same place till it broke. The number of times the films could be folded at the same place without breaking gave the value of the folding endurance.

5. Moisture Content

To check the physical stability of the film humidity conditions , accurately weighed film were placed in desiccator containing saturated solution of calcium chloride at room temperature for 24 hours..

The patches are weighed again after a specific interval until they show constant weight.

%Moisture content = $\frac{\text{Initial weight} - \text{Final weight}}{\text{Initial weight}} \times 100$

Final weight

6. Drug Content

The film of specified area was cut and added to a beaker containing 100 ml phosphate buffer pH 7.2. The medium was stirred (500 rpm) with Teflon coated magnetic bead for 5 hrs . The content were filterate was analysed by U.V. spectrophotometer at 206nm for the drug content against the blank solution .

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

STANDARD PLOT OF PREGABALIN

The standard curve of pregabalin in phosphate buffer ph 7.2 was obtained as follows

Table 2: data of absorbance vs concentration

CONCENTRATION (µg/ ml)	ABSORBANCE
2	0.098
4	0.1835
6	0.2698
8	0.3588
10	0.4422

Figure 2: Standard Calibration Curve

FT-IR Spectroscopic Study

Identification of pregabalin by FTIR spectroscopy:

Figure 3 : FTIR Spectrum of pure drug Pregabalin

Figure 4 : FTIR spectrum of pure drug Pregabalin and HPMC K15M

Figure 5 : FTIR spectrum of pure drug Pregabalin and ethyl cellulose

EVALUATION STUDIES

1. PHYSICAL APPEARANCE

The patches were visually inspected for colour, clarity, flexibility, thickness, and smoothness.

Table 3: Physical appearance pregabalin patches

FOMULATION CODE	COLOUR	CLARITY	FLEXIBILITY	SMOOTHNESS
F1	Colourless	Clear	Flexible	Smooth
F2	Colourless	Clear	Flexible	Smooth
F3	Colourless	Clear	Flexible	Smooth

2. FILM THICKNESS

The thickness of patches was determined by using screw gauge. The mean thickness was measured at different points of the film.

Table 4: thickness of sample of pregabalin patches

S.NO	FORMULATION CODE	MEAN THICKNESS(mm)
1	F1	0.178±0.3
2	F2	0.145±0.2
3	F3	0.293±0.13

WEIGHT VARIATION

The weight variation of the sample is given below in the Table 5

Table 5 : weight variation of pregabalin patches

S.NO	FORMULATION CODE	MEAN WEIGHT (gm)
1.	F1	3.345±2.1
2.	F2	2.765±1.4
3.	F3	4.698±1.8

3. FOLDING ENDURANCE

The folding endurance of the sample is given below in the **Table 6**

Table 6: folding endurance of pregabalin patches

S.NO	FORMULATION CODE	PERCENTAGE MOISTURE CONTENT(%)
1.	F1	77±2
2.	F2	89±2
3.	F3	91±1

4. DRUG CONTENT

The drug content of the samples are given below **Table 7**

Table 7: drug content of pregabalin patches

S.NO	FORMULATION CODE	PERCENTAGE DRUG CONTENT(%)
1.	F1	87.78±0.6
2.	F2	98.56±0.7
3.	F3	99.23±0.6

5. MOISTURE CONTENT

The percentage moisture content of the samples are given below in the **Table 8**

Table 8 : percentage moisture content of pregabalin patches

S.NO	FORMULATION CODE	PERCENTAGE MOISTURE CONTENT(%)
1.	F1	11.76±0.04
2.	F2	10.45±0.01
3.	F3	11.91±0.10

CONCLUSION:

The transdermal patches of pregabalin is successfully prepared by using HPMC, EC, PVP, Polyethylene glycol by solvent casting method. And it was thin, smooth, flexible. The formulation F3 was found to be best among all batches with release rate for 24 hours for treatment of epilepsy and neurological, psychiatric conditions. It was found to be increase in drug release by increasing the concentration of hydrophilic polymer HPMC.

Hence it was concluded the pregabalin transdermal patches may prove to be potential candidate for safe and effective controlled drug delivery over extended period of time.

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